

Monitoring electrical parameters inside of PV inverters

C. Camara-Viana¹, F. Sánchez-Sutil¹[0000-0001-9508-1728], A. Cano-Ortega¹[0000-0002-6440-021X], J.C. Hernández¹[0000-0001-9117-1689], S. Ruzafa-Soto¹, Eduardo Espinosa^{2,3} [0000-0002-8896-0852]

¹ Department of Electrical Engineering, University of Jaén, Campus Lagunillas s/n, Spain

²Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Universidad Católica de la Santísima Concepción, Talca 3467769, Chile

³Centro de Energía, Universidad Católica de la Santísima Concepción, Concepción 4090541, Chile

fssutil@ujaen.es

Abstract. The vast majority of inverters installed today are not monitored, or the monitoring is carried out in the AC part with sensors external to the inverter. The inverters that can be purchased on the market have an interface to extract the data with which it works. These interfaces usually work with the Modbus protocol, in their TCP/IP or RS485 bus versions. Access to this data allows access to both DC and AC parameters, as well as additional parameters such as operating temperature. Wireless technologies make it possible to send data over long distances without the installation of additional cables. This research designs a device that accesses investor data and transmits it wirelessly to the cloud.

Keywords: LPWAN, LoRa, Smart Monitoring PV Inverters.

1 Introduction

Nowadays, it is of vital importance to have real-time data from electrical installations. This becomes even more interesting in generation facilities such as PV plants or smaller scale generation in homes. Most installations are not monitored, or if they are, it is only on the AC side. It is quite difficult to find installations that have access to the DC side.

Inverters are usually monitored via applications provided by the manufacturers. These applications do not provide all the data that inverters have available. Another added problem is the rate at which the data is taken, which is usually no less than 5 minutes, which is insufficient for quality monitoring. Moreover, the data cannot be downloaded and are the property of the manufacturers, without users having access to this information.

To access all inverter data, the ModBus protocol can be used, which allows access to all stored variables. It can be accessed via RS485 or TCP/IP interface, and the data

2 C. Camara-Viana and F. Sánchez-Sutil

is then uploaded to the cloud where it can be accessed for viewing, downloading, analysis, etc. The data rate can also be reduced to better adapt it to the monitoring needs of each installation.

Inverters are often installed in locations where it is necessary to use large amounts of cable to access the inverters or where wireless coverage does not reach them. This is where LPWAN (Low-Power Wide Area Network) technologies are used, which have a long range and low power consumption. Of particular interest is the LoRa (Long-Range) network, which has a range of 5-10 km, sufficient for most domestic installations and large PV plants.

2 Related work

Before starting with the development of the equipment, it is necessary to review the state of the art in the monitoring of electrical installations, with emphasis on those that use IoT (Internet of Things) access and wireless communications.

The most widely used technology in IoT devices for monitoring electrical installations is Wi-Fi (Wireless-Fidelity), and there are several articles that describe devices that send information using this technology. Sánchez-Sutil et al. [1] developed a low-cost, open-source home meter for homes with PV installations. Medeiros et al. [2] implemented a three-phase metering device using Wi-Fi and low cost, to be installed in homes and industrial environments. Hernández et al. [3] studied the influence of data sampling frequency in electrical installations, with case studies in Spain, using Smart Meters with Wi-Fi technology. Hlaing et al. [4] built a Smart Meter with Wi-Fi and IoT connection for single-phase installations. Cano-Ortega et al. [5] developed a platform to analyse large amounts of data in the cloud from measurements in homes, PV plants and electric vehicle chargers. Salor et al. [6] implemented a mobile power quality meter for transmission facilities. Benavides et al. [7] developed a model to remotely control a microgrid based on demand-side power control.

Cano-Ortega et al. [8] realized a device to monitor the efficiency and operating conditions of induction motors in industrial environments using LoRa technology. Abete et al. [9] implemented a low-cost IoT connected meter based on the ADE7913 measurement chip. Sánchez-Sutil et al. [10] developed a control and measurement system for public lighting networks based on a LoRa network. Sánchez-Sutil et al. [11] built an energy efficiency system for public lighting under a LoRa LPWAN network. Francisco Sánchez-Sutil et al. [12] designed and tested a control and data reading device for power quality analyzers using ModBus and RS485 communication, eliminating wiring and using a wireless LoRa LPWAN network. Sánchez-Sutil et al. [13] implemented a Smart plug to monitor and control electrical devices in homes with LoRa communication. Sánchez-Sutil et al. [14] developed an energy efficiency system for irrigation systems using LoRaWAN. Sánchez-Sutil et al. [15] designed and implemented a real-time smart meter with LoRa communication. Cano-Ortega et al. [16] built a smart meter for residential environments with application of TLBO algorithm and LoRaWAN networks. Sánchez-Sutil et al. [17] developed a power quality analyzer for monitoring public lighting networks with LoRa wireless communication system.

3 Hardware design

The hardware design has sought to make a PCB (Printed Control Board) board with the smallest possible dimensions in order to facilitate installation near the inverters. The board has been designed with dual Wi-Fi and LoRa wireless communication. The design could be made with one or the other network, or both at the same time. It is also possible to make boards with only one of the two types of communication depending on the needs.

The microcontroller chosen is the Arduino Nano (AN) [18] because of its size and power, as well as its ability to work with different components. Access to Wi-Fi, and therefore to IoT via Google's Firebase [19] service, is guaranteed by a Wemos d1 mini (Wd1m) microcontroller [20]. This microcontroller is connected to a Deek-Robot datalogger model id8122 from which the measurement time is taken; as an option, the datalogger incorporates a microSD memory slot that would allow the measurements to be recorded. The LoRa network communication has been realised with a Dragino LA66 LoRaWAN Shield (LA66S) card [21]. The design is completed by a W5100 mini-Ethernet card, as the inverter chosen for the tests, model Sunny boy 3000 TL-21 from SMA, has implemented the ModBus protocol via TCP/IP.

Access to Firebase from the LoRa network is not direct, but requires the node network service as a gateway. LA66S sends the data to the PG1302 hub [22]. This hub sends the data to TTN (The Things Network) via a wired or Wi-Fi Internet connection, which is already installed on a Raspberry Pi 4 [23]. TTN has implemented a server with MQTT protocol (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport) [24] for each project, this server is connected to Node-Red, which in turn sends it to Firebase. The applications for mobile devices are enhanced with MIT App Inventor [25]. Fig. 1 shows the block diagram of the device.

Fig. 1. Device block diagram.

4 C. Camara-Viana and F. Sánchez-Sutil

The connection diagram of the device is shown in Fig. 2. The connection between the inverter and the W5100 Ethernet card is made via network cable with RJ45 connection. W5100 is connected to AN for information exchange. AN sends measurement command to W5100, once received the data is sent to Wd1m via the serial port. Wd1m reads the measurement time and uploads it to Firebase. In turn, it sends the information to LA66S to send it to the PG1302 concentrator, which uploads the data to TTN, with the MQTT server it is received by Node-Red and sent to Firebase. Fig. 3 shows the PCB board mounted and sending data.

Fig. 2. Connection diagram of the inverter data extraction circuit and sending to the cloud via Wi-Fi and/or LoRa.

Fig. 3. Assembled PCB board of the inverter access device.

4 Software design

4.1 Arduino Nano programming

AN deals with ModBus communication with the inverter, in this case under TCP/IP protocol, which is the one chosen by the manufacturer. To start the program, it must start (i) the ModBus system; (ii) the W5100 network card; (iii) the serial port. Subsequently, the work it does is to read the serial port, if it receives a measurement command from W1dm, it sends the command to the inverter, waits for the inverter's response and sends the measurement data to W1dm. Fig. 4 shows the flow diagram for AN.

Fig. 4. AN main flow chart.

4.2 W1dm programming

W1dm is the center of the measurement device. First, W1dm must perform initialization, preparing (i) the real-time clock; (ii) the serial port for communication with AN; (iii) start the virtual serial port for communication with LA66S; (iv) start the Wi-Fi adapter. Subsequently, W1dm must take care of sending measurement command to AN, receiving data from AN, taking the measurement time, sending the measurement data to Firebase and sending the measurement data to LA66S. Fig. 5 shows the flowchart of W1dm.

6 C. Camara-Viana and F. Sánchez-Sutil

Fig. 5. W1dm main flow chart.

4.3 Programming Node-Network

The LoRa network cannot connect directly to Firebase to have the data in the cloud, but it is sent directly to TTN which implements an MQTT server for each device. To connect TTN with Firebase, Node-Red is used as a gateway. For this purpose Node-Red waits for an event from TTN, collects and converts the necessary data and sends it to Firebase. In addition to the electrical data, the LoRa network parameters are also collected for communication statistics and to improve the network. Fig. 6 shows part of the Node-Red program, corresponding to the LoRa system variables.

Fig. 6. Node-Red program.

4.4 Programming for data download

The data is downloaded and deleted from Firebase on a daily basis, so as not to take up the free Firebase quota for each project, which amounts to 1 GB of information. To do this, a Python program has been implemented that accesses each project, downloads the information in json format, which is how Firebase offers it, converts it to csv and deletes it from Firebase. The program runs at 2am each day to download the previous day's data, using the Windows task scheduler. If for some reason a day is not downloaded, it searches for previous days and downloads and deletes all the data. Fig. 7 shows the flow diagram

Fig. 7. Download data program.

5 Results

5.1 Test equipment

To perform the tests, the PV installation of the Department of Electrical Engineering of the University of Jaén has been used. The installation is located on the terrace of the A3 building of the Campus de las Lagunillas in Jaén. The installation consists of 10 Axitec model AC-270P/156-60 panels providing 2.97 kWp, connected to a grid-connected SMA Sunny boy 3000 TL-21 inverter, located in the A3-265 laboratory. Fig. 8 Fig. 8 shows the installation for carrying out the tests.

8 C. Camara-Viana and F. Sánchez-Sutil

Fig. 8. (a) Arrangement of the solar panels; (b) location of the installation in the A3 building; (c) inverter installed in the A3-265 laboratory.

5.2 Data obtained

The information obtained can be represented and analyzed to improve the monitored system and improve equipment monitoring. This information is downloaded daily at 2 am and saved in csv format.

Fig. 9 shows the data measured on 11 July 2024. Part (a) shows the DC voltage which is maintained at a value of 70 VDC while the generator is not generating, then the voltage rises to around 300 VAC, the AC voltage remains constant at around 240 VAC which is the reference voltage of the grid to which the inverter is connected. The currents are shown in part (b), where it can clearly be seen that the AC output current is higher than the DC input current. The DC power is higher than the AC power, as shown in part (c). On the other hand, the efficiency is lower in the DC part than in the AC part as can be seen in part (d). Finally, the operating temperature of the inverter is shown in part (e) which, as can be seen, coincides in shape with the daily generation

curve, with the temperature increasing with the increase in power handled by the inverter.

Fig. 9. Data measured on 2024/07/11. (a) voltage; (b) current; (c) power; (d) performance; (e) inverter temperature.

5.3 Data visualization

A Dashboard has been created to monitor the inverter data as well as the LoRa grid parameters. The data is refreshed every 10 seconds and the display range is 1 day. The dashboard has been realized in Node-Red. Fig. 10 shows the inverter dashboard and Fig. 11 the LoRa network dashboard.

10 C. Camara-Viana and F. Sánchez-Sutil

Fig. 10. Inverter Dashboard created in Node-Red.

Fig. 11. Dashboard for LoRa network data created in Node-Red.

On the other hand, an app for mobile devices has also been developed for real-time visualisation of the data generated. The application is made in MIT App Inventor for the Android operating system. Fig. 12 shows a screenshot of the application.

Fig. 12. App for display on Android devices.

Acknowledgments. The authors acknowledge the support provided by the Thematic Network 723RT0150 “Red para la integración a gran escala de energías renovables en sistemas eléctricos (RIBIERSE-CYTED)” financed by the call for Thematic Networks of the CYTED (Ibero-American Program of Science and Technology for Development) for 2022.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article. This research was funded by the Council of Andalucía (Junta de Andalucía. Consejería de Transformación Económica, Industria, Conocimiento y Universidades. Secretaría General de Universidades, Investigación y Tecnología) through project ProyExcel 00381.

References

1. F. Sanchez-Sutil, A. Cano-Ortega, J.C. Hernández, C. Rus-Casas. Development and Calibration of an Open Source, Low-Cost Power Smart Meter Prototype for PV Household-Prosumers. *Electronics*, 8, 878 (2019). doi:10.3390/electronics8080878
2. Medeiros, E. L., Costa, E. G., Lira, G. R., Alves, A. C., & Diniz, C. V. A Low Cost Power Quality Meter over the Internet. 2016 17th International Conference on Harmonics and Quality of Power. doi:10.1109/ICHQP.2016.7783395
3. A. Cano-Ortega, F. Sánchez-Sutil. Monitoring of the Efficiency and Conditions of Induction Motor Operations by Smart Meter Prototype Based on a LoRa Wireless Network. *Electronics*, 8, 1040 (2019). doi:10.3390/electronics8091040

12 C. Camara-Viana and F. Sánchez-Sutil

4. J. C. Hernandez, F. Sanchez-Sutil, A. Cano-Ortega, C. R. Baier. Influence of Data Sampling Frequency on Household Consumption Load Profile Features: A Case Study in Spain. *Sensors* 20, 6034 (2020). doi:10.3390/s20216034
5. A. Cano-Ortega I, M. A. Garcia-Cumbreras, F. Sánchez-Sutil, J. C. Hernández. A Platform for Analysing Huge Amounts of Data from Households, Photovoltaics, and Electrical Vehicles: From Data to Information. *Electronics*, 11, 3991 (2022). doi.org/10.3390/electronics11233991
6. Ö. Salor, S. Buhan, Ö. Ünsar, B. Boyrazog. Mobile monitoring system to take nationwide PQ measurements on electricity transmission systems. *Measurement*. 42, 501–515 (2009). 10.1016/j.measurement.2008.09.007.
7. Dario Benavides, Paul Arévalo, Antonio Cano Ortega, Francisco Sánchez-Sutil, Edison Villa-Avila. Energy Management Model for a Remote Microgrid Based on Demand-Side Energy Control. *Energies* 17, 170 (2024). doi.org/10.3390/en17010170.
8. A. Cano-Ortega, F. Sánchez-Sutil. Monitoring of the Eciency and Conditions of Induction Motor Operations by Smart Meter Prototype Based on a LoRa Wireless Network. *Electronics* 8,1040 (2019). doi:10.3390/electronics8091040
9. Abate, F., Carratù, M., Liguori, C., & Paciello, V.. A low cost smart power meter for IoT. *Measurement*, 136, 59-66 (2019). doi:10.1016/j.measurement.2018.12.069.
10. F. Sánchez Sutil, Antonio Cano-Ortega. Smart Public Lighting Control and Measurement System Using LoRa Network. *Electronics* 9,124 (2020). doi:10.3390/electronics9010124
11. F. Sanchez-Sutil, A. Cano-Ortega. Smart regulation and efficiency energy system for street lighting with LoRa LPWAN. *Sustainable Cities and Society* 70 102912 (2021). doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2021.102912
12. Francisco Sánchez-Sutil, Antonio Cano-Ortega. Design and Testing of a Power Analyzer Monitor and Programming Device in Industries with a LoRa LPWAN Network. *Electronics* 10, 453 (2021). doi.org/10.3390/electronics10040453
13. F. Sanchez-Sutil, A. Cano-Ortega. Smart plug for monitoring and controlling electrical devices with a wireless communication system integrated in a LoRaWAN. *Expert Systems With Applications* 213, 118976 (2023). doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2022.118976
14. Francisco Sánchez-Sutil, Antonio Cano-Ortega. Smart Control and Energy Efficiency in Irrigation Systems Using LoRaWAN. *Sensors* 21, 7041 (2021). doi.org/10.3390/s21217041
15. Francisco Sánchez-Sutil, Antonio Cano-Ortega, Jesús C. Hernández. Design and Implementation of a Smart Energy Meter Using a LoRa Network in Real Time. *Electronics* 10, 3152 (2021). doi.org/10.3390/electronics10243152
16. A. Cano-Ortega, F. Sánchez-Sutil, J. C. Hernández. Smart meter for residential electricity consumption with TLBO algorithm for LoRaWAN. *Electrical Engineering* 105, 2021-2040 (2023). doi.org/10.1007/s00202-023-01783-w
17. F. Sanchez-Sutil, A. Cano-Ortega. Development and implementation of a PQ analyser to monitoring public lighting installations with a LoRa wireless system. *Internet of Things* 22 100711 (2023). doi.org/10.1016/j.iot.2023.100711.
18. Arduino Homepage, <https://store.arduino.cc/products/arduino-nano>, last accessed 2024/08/09
19. Firebase Homepage, <https://firebase.google.com/?hl=es>, last accessed 2024/08/09
20. Wemos electronics Homepage, https://www.wemos.cc/en/latest/d1/d1_mini.html, last accessed 2024/08/09
21. Dragino Homepage, <https://www.dragino.com/products/lora/item/231-la66-lorawan-shield.html>, last accessed 2024/08/09
22. Dragino Homepage, <https://www.dragino.com/products/lora/item/223-pg1302.html>, last accessed 2024/08/09

Monitoring electrical parameters inside of PV inverters 13

23. Raspbetry Pi Homepage, <https://www.raspberrypi.com/products/raspberry-pi-4-model-b/>, last accessed 2024/08/09
24. MQTT Homepage, <https://mqtt.org>, last accessed 2024/08/09
25. MIT App Inventor Homepage, <https://appinventor.mit.edu>, last accessed 2024/08/09